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STUDY OF THE KINETICS OF THE PROCESS OF DEHYDRATION OF GLYCEROL INTO ACROLEIN

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of studying the study of the kinetic patterns of the process of dehydration of glycerol into acrolein. The process of dehydration of glycerol is a heterogeneous catalytic reaction. A heterogeneous oxide-type catalyst was used as a catalyst. On the basis of the proposed kinetic model, the optimal conditions for carrying out the process of dehydration of glycerol were found.

Keywords: process, vapor-phase dehydration, catalysis, kinetic model, glycerol

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ КИНЕТИКИ ПРОЦЕССА ДЕГИДРАТАЦИИ ГЛИЦЕРИНА В АКРОЛЕИН

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются вопросы изучения кинетических закономерностей процесса дегидратации глицерина в акролеин. Процесс дегидратации глицерина является

гетерогенно-каталитической реакцией. В качестве катализатора использовался гетерогенный катализатор оксидного типа. На базе предложенной кинетической модели были найдены оптимальные условия проведения процесса дегидратации глицерина.

Ключевые слова: процесс, парофазная дегидратация, катализатор, кинетическая модель, глицерин

In 2010, the world production of acrylic acid amounted to 5.1 million tons [1]. Another important area of processing is the production of methionine, which is used as a feed additive [2], the global demand for which is estimated at 450-500 thousand tons per year and is constantly growing [3]. Acrolein and its derivatives are used in the production of 1,3-propanediol, used as a feedstock for the production of medicines, herbicides, flavorings and plasticizers. The main ways to obtain acrolein are catalytic aldol condensation of formaldehyde with acetaldehyde; vapor-phase oxidation of propylene; vapor-phase oxidation of propane; dehydration of glycerol.

Glycerin is widely used in the food industry, in the production of detergents and cosmetics, plastics, agriculture and other industries. However, today the production volumes of this product have become many times higher than the volumes of its traditional processing [4-8].

The most promising way to obtain acrolein is the vapor phase dehydration of glycerol. The aim of this work was study of the main patterns of the course of the dehydration process glycerin using a heterogeneous catalyst, namely but the establishment of the dependences of the conversion of the feedstock and the selectivity of the formation of the target product on the parameters.

Kinetic experiments were carried out in the temperature range 320-350^o C and the concentration of glycerin in the feed stream is 10-30% by weight. The process of vapor phase dehydration of glycerin is a heterogeneous catalytic reaction. A heterogeneous catalyst with a composition of 0.5B₂O₃/γ-Al₂O₃ was used as a catalyst. The conducted studies have shown that when using a catalyst with a grain size of less than 4.0 mm, the effect of internal diffusion on the rate of the process of vapor phase dehydration of glycerin can be excluded. Therefore, when studying the kinetic regularities of the process under study, the fraction of catalyst

grains 2.0-3.0 mm was used. Kinetic studies were carried out on a laboratory installation with a flow reactor.

A catalyst suspension was loaded into the reactor between the layers of the inert nozzle. The catalyst was precrushed to produce granules with a size of 2.0-3.0 mm. All experiments were carried out at 375°C and atmospheric pressure. The temperature deviation during the process did not exceed 0.5°C. The load on the catalyst for pure glycerin was 0.0242 l/(gcat*min). A 20% aqueous glycerin solution was supplied at a constant flow rate of 0.2 cm³/min. Reactor was installed in thermostat, after which the catalyst was preliminarily kept at a given temperature in the nitrogen current for 1 hour. Further, the nitrogen supply was stopped, and with a constant flow rate, an aqueous solution of glycerin was supplied to the evaporator 3 with the help of a pump H. The steam stream coming out of the reactor was condensed in a cryostatic (-20°C) reverse refrigerator 3. The reaction products were collected in a sampler. Sampling was performed every hour. Based on the accepted reaction mechanism of the glycerol vapor phase dehydration process, the reaction rate for key substances can be calculated as follows:

$$r_1 = \frac{F_1}{m_{\text{кат}}} \quad (1)$$

$$r_2 = \frac{F_2}{m_{\text{кат}}} \quad (2)$$

$$r_3 = \frac{F_3}{m_{\text{кат}}} \quad (3)$$

$$r_4 = \frac{F_4 * X}{m_{\text{кат}}} \quad (4)$$

where r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4 is the rate of formation of acrolein, acetone, acetaldehyde and glycerin consumption, respectively, mol/(min *g.cat);

F_1, F_2, F_3 – is the molar flow of acrolein, acetone, acetaldehyde formed at the exit from the reaction medium, respectively, mol/min;

F_4 –initial molar flow of glycerin, mol/min; $m_{\text{кат}}$ - is the mass of the catalyst, g;

X - is the conversion of glycerin.

Thus, the following kinetic equations were obtained:

– the rate of acrolein formation: $r_1 = k_{0,1} * e^{-\frac{E_{a,1}}{RT}} * C_4$;

– the rate of acetone formation: $r_2 = k_{0,2} * e^{-\frac{E_{a,2}}{RT}} * C_4$;

– the rate of formation of acetaldehyde: $r_3 = k_{0,3} * e^{-\frac{E_{a,3}}{RT}} * C_4$;

– glycerin consumption rate: $r_4 = k_{0,4} * e^{-\frac{E_{a,4}}{RT}} * C_4$.

where r_1, r_2, r_3 is the rate of formation of acrolein, acetone and acetaldehyde, respectively, mol/(min*g.cat);

r_4 is the rate of glycerin consumption, mol/(min*g.cat);

$k_{0,i}$ – is a pre-exponential multiplier;

C_4 - glycerol concentration at the exit from the reaction zone, mol/l;

$E_{a,i}$ - activation energy, J/mol;

R - is the universal gas constant, J/(mol*K);

T - is the temperature, K;

Taking into account the stoichiometry and the kinetic equations given, the rates of change of the molar fluxes of the reaction mass components will be as follows, mol/(min*g.cat)

$$\frac{dF_1}{dm_{\text{кат}}} = r_1$$

$$\frac{dF_2}{dm_{\text{кат}}} = r_2$$

$$\frac{dF_3}{dm_{\text{кат}}} = r_3$$

$$\frac{dF_4}{dm_{\text{кат}}} = r_4$$

$$\frac{dF_5}{dm_{\text{кат}}} = r_5 - (r_1 + r_2 + r_3)$$

Where r_5 is the rate of formation of by products, mol/(min*g.cat)

F_5 is the mole flow of by products, mol/min.

The results of mathematical processing according to the proposed model are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Results of mathematical processing of experimental data

Parameter	Meaning
$k_{0,1}$	3.44×10^2
$k_{0,2}$	2.38×10^3
$k_{0,3}$	5.47×10^5
$k_{0,4}$	1.11×10^4
$E_{a,1}$ kJ/mol	52.19
$E_{a,2}$ kJ/mol	54.93
$E_{a,3}$ kJ/mol	93.03
$E_{a,4}$ kJ/mol	64.31

The adequacy of the obtained equations was evaluated using the Fisher criterion. Experimental and calculated rates of consumption and formation of key substances according to the model are presented in Table 2

Table 2 – Experimental and calculated by the model of the rate of consumption and formation of key substances

t, °C	The concentration of glycerin, %wt	Xr, %	Acrolein formation rate, r×10 ³ , mole/(min×g .cat)		Acetaldehyde formation rate, r×10 ³ , mole/(min×g .cat)		Glycerin consumption rate, r×10 ³ , mole/(min×g .cat)	
			Experimental	estimated	Experimental	estimated	Experimental	estimated
320	20	9,6	0,5262	0,5526	0,0367	0,0365	0,8740	0,7762
	22	8,7	0,5331	0,5844	0,0403	0,0392	0,8754	0,8208
	24	8,2	0,5553	0,6155	0,0407	0,0418	0,9044	0,8645
	28	7,5	0,6056	0,6764	0,0458	0,0471	0,9751	0,9500
	30	7,0	0,6123	0,7064	0,0500	0,0497	0,9797	0,9922
325	20	10,0	0,5745	0,5964	0,0401	0,0424	0,9104	0,8594
	22	9,2	0,5879	0,6308	0,0463	0,0455	0,9258	0,9090
	24	8,5	0,5981	0,6645	0,0459	0,0486	0,9357	0,9576
	28	7,7	0,6457	0,7305	0,0501	0,0547	1,0011	1,0527
	30	7,2	0,6510	0,7630	0,0504	0,0578	1,0077	1,0995
330	10	14,9	0,4363	0,4341	0,0324	0,0300	0,6621	0,6415
	12	13,7	0,4882	0,4803	0,0360	0,0341	0,7341	0,7097
	14	12,7	0,5297	0,5235	0,0399	0,0380	0,7978	0,7737
	16	11,8	0,5678	0,5647	0,0434	0,0418	0,8512	0,8345
	18	11,3	0,6128	0,6042	0,0442	0,0455	0,9215	0,8929
	20	11,0	0,6730	0,6424	0,0461	0,0491	1,0015	0,9493
	22	10,2	0,6938	0,6796	0,0482	0,0527	1,0264	1,0044

On the basis of the proposed kinetic equations, optimal conditions for the process of vapor phase dehydration of glycerin were found and determined. The results of optimization of technological parameters of the process of vapor phase dehydration of glycerin are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 – Technological parameters of the process of vapor phase dehydration of glycerin

Parameter	Meaning
Temperature, °C	320
The concentration of glycerol in the feed stream, % wt.	31
Catalyst load, l/(q _{kat} ·min)	0.0341
The degree of conversion of glycerol, %	99.8
Selectivity of acrolein formation, %	68.1

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